

Original Article

COMPETENCIES REQUIRED FOR EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF PRIVATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS BY RETIRED BUSINESS EDUCATORS FOR SUSTAINABLE JOB CREATION IN IMO STATE

Dr. Ugocha, I. C., Prof. Alio A. N. and Dr. Ohagwu, G. C.

Enugu State University of
Science and Technology,
Esut.

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Abstract

The central purpose of the study was to determine the competencies required for effective management of private secondary schools by retired Business Educators for sustainable job creation in Imo State. The study was carried out in Imo State, Nigeria using a descriptive survey research design. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The population for the study comprised 410 private school Business Education teachers, in the 27 Local Government Areas of Imo State. The instrument used for data collection was a 61-item structured questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument was structured using a four-point rating scale. The instrument was validated by the three experts, two of them from Business and Entrepreneurship Education Department and one in Measurement and Evaluation option from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education both in Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient which yielded 0.78. Out of 410 copies of the questionnaire distributed 396 copies were properly filled and used for data analysis representing 96.59% return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test was used to test the 12 null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance at 394 degree of freedom. The study revealed that all the items under the planning competencies, organisation competencies and administration knowledge were highly required by Business Educator Retirees for effective management of private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State. Based on the findings, some implications were deduced and it was recommended among others that the Business Educators retirees going into private school business should acquire the identified competencies for effective management. Also, the government and concerned bodies in management of retirement should empower the teachers through retirement training on the competencies for managing private school businesses.

Keywords: Competencies; Effective Management; Retired Business Educators; Sustainable Job Creation

Introduction

Unemployment as a global phenomenon is on the increase especially in Nigeria. Nigeria is bedeviled

with a plethora of problems which despite her oil wealth, its development will be a mirage. Unemployment is one of the developmental problems that is plaguing every developing economy in this twenty-first century, and Nigeria is inclusive. Unemployment according to Edward (2019) is people above a specified age not being in paid employment or self-employment but currently available for work during the reference period. Unemployment is measured by the unemployment rate, which is the number of people who are unemployed as a percentage of the labour force. Those of the unemployable age are yet to be employed and the retirees seem not to have hope of re-employment. It is advisable and appropriate to start preparation for retirement immediately one gains employment in Nigeria's already saturated labour market. This is necessary because the employees need to plan, adopt and implement strategies to ease the pain and problems associated with retirement, since retirement from active service is unavoidable. This is why Akuraun & Kenneth (2013), opined that many employees perceived retirement as a threat rather than an issue of interest.

Retirement means joy and relaxation from full time work. This means that retirement if properly managed will enhance the living standard of the retirees. Ugocha (2017), defined retirement as a well-known institutionalized sequence in both Private and Public Institution when workers cease to become members of their employment organizations after an established number of years of service or age. When an individual attains the age between fifty or sixty years without appreciating the realities of old age and that one day he will retire from active work, adjustment that follows becomes very manifest. As the future is unpredictable and the only thing certain about it is that, it will be different, workers should endeavor to think ahead of time and prepare as prospective retirees.

Retirees are adults who have been disengaged from the initial employment after long services but are still

willing and able to continue their existence in a desirable but less strenuous occupations with affordable investment (Asogwa, Isigwa and Obetta, 2013). Offordile (2018) added that engagement of the retirees in a sustainable occupation requires some retirement plans to help provide a livable income when an individual stops working. Retirees' participation in the labour force has increased greatly since the 20th Century (Ajayi, 2013) and the percentage of retirees engaged in the paid labour force is increasing rapidly. Therefore, effort must be made to ensure that the competencies for engaging retirees in running a Private Secondary School and other entrepreneurship business such as poultry farming, fishery, sachet water business, cassava production, snail rearing, rice farming, hotel business, fast-food eatery, investing in property, professional car wash, dry cleaning services, sales of building materials, transport business etc. are identified. According to Hornby (2014), Private School is a school that is not supported by government money, where education must be paid for by the children's parents. Private Schools, also known as Independent Schools, non-governmental, or non-State School are not administered by local, state or national government. Thus, they retain the right to select their students and are funded in whole or in part by charging their students tuition, rather than relying on mandatory taxation through public (government) funding (Ugocha, 2014). Ugocha added that in some Private Schools, students may be able to get Scholarships which make the cost cheaper, depending on the talent the students may have (e.g sport scholarships, art scholarship, and academic scholarship). Private School is made up of Nursery, Primary and Secondary Schools. The aims of running private school can be summarized as follows: (a) for self-fulfillment which is the desire to make valuable contributions to the community to which one belongs. (b) to keep oneself busy after retirement and to continue to be relevant in ones field of endeavor. (c) to produce learners who will be credited worthy to the school and Community

at large in behaviour. (d) to equip the learners with the basic skills to make them successful even in their private lives and (e) responsible citizens capable of making valuable contributions to the larger community in future (Udeji, 2019). To achieve the above stated aims is dependent upon effective management of the school.

According to Akuraun and Kenneth (2013) effective management is the art or process of influencing people to perform assigned tasks willingly, efficiently and competently, thereby fostering a work environment where everyone has the ability to excel. Effective Management starts with self-knowledge and deep understanding of business goals. This is because, those who work must effectively work with, and through other people to produce the most outstanding results. Every private school is expected to have a school manager or proprietor who plan, direct and organize the activities of the school. The purpose of a school manager is to achieve results through the activities of other people with the application of strategic planning which is an essential part to the concept of entrepreneurial development of individuals, which implies expertise in competencies to achieve a goal (Eze, 2016). The growth and functionality of a school depends on the competency possessed by the managers.

Competency is the successful performance of a task through the use of knowledge, skills, attitude and judgment. Duroyaje and Onasoga (2014), added that competency is the state of being functionally skillful in performance of one's duty. To be competent therefore, means that the individual has acquired knowledge, skills and attitudes which are required for performing successfully at a specified proficiency level in any given work or trade. In the context of this study, competencies refer to identified knowledge and skills required by Business Educator retirees for effective Management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State.

Engaging Business Educator retirees in Private Schools seek to empower individuals and groups of

people with the skills they need to effect change in their economic condition and within their livelihood. It also deals with identifying, harnessing local community resources, opportunities and stimulating sustainable economic, employment activity. According to Agbaghoroma and Okose (2017), sustainability is the ability or capacity of something to be maintained. It is about taking what we need to live now, without jeopardizing the potential for people in the future to meet their needs. Mbah and Onoh (2016) opined that for an economic activity to be sustainable, it should be able to continue forever, be it business venture or job opportunity.

Ugocha (2017), defined jobs as all activities that generate actual or imputed income, monetary or in kind including salaried activities. The International Labour Organizations (ILO) (2017) and its Constituents (that is representatives of government, employers, and workers) pioneered the concept of decent work to promote work as "a source of personal dignity, family stability, peace in the community, democracies that deliver for people, and economic growth that expands opportunities for productive jobs and enterprise development". According to ILO (2017), the overall goal of decent work is to effect positive changes in people's lives through sustainable job creation and employment. Sustainable job creation refers to the process of generating jobs that contribute to sustainable development goals. In other words, sustainable job creation is a process that promotes economic growth, social inclusion and environmental protection (Obayi, 2014), and this is why business educators need to have the required competencies in order to function adequately in the performance of their job.

Business Educators are teachers who teach courses in Business Administration and management, such as accounting, finance, human resources, labour relations, marketing and operations research (Ezeabii, 2017). Business Education has been considered from different perspective because there seems to be no standard definition or universal agreement as to what

it stands for. Ezeabii and Agomou (2017) defined Business Education as the component of vocational Technical Education programme that prepares an individual for career in business and also to be an intelligent consumer of economic goods and services. In this era of globalization, Obayi (2014) stated that Business Education contributes greatly in the economic development of any nation and has become an indispensable tool for development. There are Business Educators in Imo State.

Imo State is located in the South Eastern geopolitical zone of Nigeria, and it came into existence in 1976 along with other new states created under the leadership of the late Military ruler of Nigeria, Late Gen. Murtala Mohammadu, having been previously part of East-Central State. The State is named after the Imo Rivers, and part of it was split off in 1991 as Abia State, and another part became Ebony State (nigeriazipcodes.com). Imo State is made up 27 Local Government Areas with a population of over 5,408,756 and land areas square kilometer of 5,288 (Business Ball, 2019). Some business investment opportunities in Imo State are palm oil production, Sales of gadgets, repairs and sales of phone, raw food business, farming business, pharmacy business, boutique business, hospitality business, Private School business etc.

Retirees in Nigeria face disheartening situations after several years of serving their fatherland and the case of retirees in Imo State is not an exception (Udeji, 2019). In some cases, these retirees from school system try to open private schools to improve their economic base and quality of life but at some point, fail because they do not possess the needed competencies. Akuraun and Kenneth (2013) pointed that the establishment of any profitable educational organization, the entrepreneur needs to acquire the competencies in the area of planning competencies, organizational skills, administration skills, Information and Communication Technology (ICT), classroom management skills financial management skills. Planning involves the selection from alternative

courses of action and available resources that is best option suitable for the achievement of these objectives. Planning is the process of preparing a set of decisions for action in the future. Ekwueme, Mbah and Onoh (2018) defined planning as a process of preparing a set of decision for action in the future, directed at achieving goals by preferable means. Planning is regarded as a vital step in business establishment without which success cannot be achieved.

In addition to planning is the organizational skills in the establishment of private schools. Organizational skills refer to your ability to stay focused on different tasks and use your time, energy, strength, mental capacity, physical space, etc. effectively and efficiently in order to achieve the desired outcome. Macieje (2020), added that these skills are essential for any smart leader who wishes to be more organized in everything that he does. The study focused on determining the planning competencies and organizational competencies as needed for the establishment of establishment of private school. It is imperative to note that lack of these competencies by the Business Educators retirees have affected their ability in the establishment and management of private secondary schools for job creation.

However, these competencies in the establishment of private schools by these retirees are not gender sensitive as both male and female teachers (retirees) need them. Also, the retirement system is not gender sensitive as male and female teachers retire from their services and some still look healthy looking for projective area to invest their energy. Considering their acquired skills and the enormous roles retirees play in their different families and the society at large, there is dire need for engagement of these retirees in economic activities for sustainable living and job creation on retirement. An empirical study of this nature must be based on theory. The theoretical framework of the study anchored on the Management Theory. The theory of management in this study focused on the adaptation management principles in

the establishment of private schools for job creation for Business Educators' Retirees. Management theory emphasized that entrepreneurs (Business Educators' Retirees) have individual specific resources that facilitates the recognition of new opportunities and the assembling of new resources for the emerging firm. Against this backdrop, it is pertinent to identify the competencies required for effective management of private secondary schools for sustainable job creation for Business Educators' Retirees in Imo State. This forms the gap the present study filled.

Statement of the Problem

It is worrisome to note that a good number of retirees (including Business Educators Retirees) grope and wander in search of livelihood after successfully and passionately serving their fathers' land for a considerable number of years. They find it difficult to meet other family needs such as feeding, children's school fees payment, house rent, power and medical payments etc. This is because, during this period of retirement, the retirees' monthly pensions are small and inconsistent, and some of the retirees who have no other source of the income perceive retirement as nightmare. This is why some of them are prone to frustration and lots of ailments such as insomnia, high blood pressure and death and as a result, their conditions constitute an economic and emotional insecurity to the society.

The incessant and increasing cases of economic hardship and frustration of retirees in Imo State is alarming and worrisome. This scenario could be as a result of deficiency in the required competencies to effectively manage Private Secondary School businesses which would meet their basic family needs, make them employers of labour, and help reduce the unemployment quagmire among the country's teeming population. Some of the business Educators' retirees in Imo State started business of Private Schools in the previous years and later closed down. The fear of failure and continuous opening and closing necessitated the need to identify the competencies required for sustainability. The

researcher is bothered about this and it is against this backdrop that the need arose to determine the competencies required by Business Educators' Retirees for effective management of private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State. This forms the problem of the present study.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the competencies required for effective management of private secondary schools by retired Business Educators for sustainable job creation in Imo State. Specifically, the study sought to determine the:

1. Planning competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation by retired Business Educators in Imo State.
2. Organizational competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creations by retired Business Educators in Imo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the planning competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation by retired Business Educators in Imo State?
2. What are the organizational competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation by retired Business Educators in Imo State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significance difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Educators' Retirees with respect to planning competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State.

H₀₂: A significant difference does not exist between the mean scores of male and female Business Educators'

Retirees with respect to organizational competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State.

Method

This study adopted a census survey research design. A survey research design is a method of sociological investigation that uses questions based on statistical surveys to collect information about how people think and act (Nwaorgu, 2015). This design was adopted due to the polychotomous instrument used and the opinions of the business educators were sought for. The area of the study was Imo State of Nigeria. The population comprised 410 private secondary school Business Educators, in the 27 Local Government Areas of Imo State. The population was determined based on the field survey conducted by the researcher. The number was manageable and as such, there was no sampling. The data collection was carried out using 20 item structured questionnaire developed by the researcher based on the review of related literature with the help of four research assistants. The instrument was validated by the three experts, two of them from Business and Entrepreneurship Education

Department and one in Measurement and Evaluation option from Department of Mathematics and Computer Education both in Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and Technology, Enugu. Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability coefficient which yielded 0.78. This 0.78 coefficient is in-line with Uzoagulu (2013) that reliability index of 0.60 to 1 shows that the instrument is highly reliable. Weighted mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. Decisions on the research questions were made using the lower and upper limits of the mean based on a four-point scale. The standard deviation was used to determine the homogeneity or otherwise of the opinions of the respondents.

Results

The results of the study obtained were presented in Tables based on the research questions and hypotheses that guided the study (see table 1-4).

Research Question 1

What are the planning competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation by Retired Business Educators in Imo State?

Table 1: Mean Scores and standard deviation of teachers on the planning competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation for Retired Business Educators in Imo State

S/ N	Planning competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation. The skills are ability to;	Male N=137		Female N= 259		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
1	Formulate specific objectives for the private school	3.07	0.68	3.11	0.64	3.09	0.66	HR
2	Conduct a feasibility study for the school	3.09	0.74	3.09	0.71	3.09	0.73	HR
3	Advertisement of the school for admission and growth	3.07	0.75	3.03	0.69	3.05	0.72	HR
4	Obtain relevant information from experienced educationists	3.05	0.79	3.03	0.73	3.04	0.76	HR
5	Identify source of finance for starting the school	3.11	0.73	3.05	0.67	3.08	0.71	HR
6	Select a suitable location for the school	3.01	0.73	3.01	0.69	3.01	0.72	HR
7	Arrange for necessary equipment and facilities for the school	3.04	0.70	3.00	0.65	3.02	0.68	HR

8	Obtain permission from the State Ministry of Education to start a private school	3.05	0.67	3.10	0.67	3.07	0.67	HR
9	Choose whether to run a boarding or day school or both	3.59	0.62	3.56	0.67	3.58	0.64	VHR
10	Determine the grade levels for your private school.	3.15	0.71	3.14	0.70	3.15	0.71	HR
Cluster Mean/SD		3.12	0.71	3.11	0.68	3.12	0.70	HR

X = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; VHR = Very Highly Required; HR = Highly Required

The analysis of data presented in Table 1 above shows that overall mean rating of item nine has mean rating of 3.58 indicating very highly required. The remaining items have mean rating ranging from 3.01 to 3.15 showing highly required. This means that the respondents view the items as the planning competencies highly required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation by Retired Business Educators in Imo State. The overall cluster mean of 3.12 further indicates that the items are the planning

competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation by Retired Business Educators in Imo State. The low standard deviation of 0.70 indicates that the respondents have similar opinion to the items.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the no significance difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Educator Retirees with respect to planning competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State.

Table 2: Summary of t-test analysis of mean ratings of male and female Business Educator Retirees with respect to planning competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	137	0.060	394	0.952	0.03647	0.60386	NS
Female	259						

The result of t-test analysis in Table 2 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 394 degree of freedom for the 10 items is 0.060 with a significant value of 0.952. Since the significant value of 0.952 is more than the 0.05 level of significance the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference regarding the items on the mean scores of male and female Business Educator Retirees with respect to planning competencies

required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State.

Research Question 2

What are the organizational competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation by Retired Business Educators in Imo State?

Table 3: Mean ratings and standard deviation on the organizational competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation by Retired Business Educators in Imo State

S / N	Organizational competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation include ability to;	Male N=137		Female N= 259		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
1	recruit qualified teachers	3.0	0.6	3.0	0.62	3.05	0.65	HR
1		7	6	1				
1	select an experienced management staff	3.2	0.6	3.1	0.68	3.19	0.69	HR
2		3	9	4				
1	apply effective supervision of activities of the school	3.0	0.6	3.0	0.63	3.05	0.65	HR
3		8	6	1				
1	appoint a seasoned guidance councilor	2.9	0.6	3.0	0.66	2.98	0.65	HR
4		7	5	0				
1	form functional School Board Management Committee (SBMC)	3.0	0.6	3.0	0.67	3.06	0.67	HR
5		7	7	6				
1	organize suitable train the trainers' workshop for teachers	3.0	0.6	3.0	0.67	3.01	0.68	HR
6		1	8	2				
1	apply management by objectives (MBO) for effective performance of staff	3.0	0.7	2.9	0.65	3.01	0.69	HR
7		4	1	7				
1	Use reward to encourage commitment among staff	3.0	0.6	3.0	0.66	3.02	0.67	HR
8		2	7	3				
1	pay salaries promptly	3.0	0.6	3.0	0.66	3.07	0.68	HR
9		6	9	8				
2	ensure suitable extra-curricular activities like sports, etc. in the school	3.1	0.6	3.0	0.62	3.11	0.64	HR
0		2	5	8				
	Cluster Mean/SD	3.0	0.6	3.0	0.65	3.06	0.67	HR
		7	7	5				

The data presented in Table 3 indicates that overall item mean ratings ranges from 2.98 to 3.19 depicting highly required. This shows that the items are the organizational competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation by Retired Business Educators in Imo State. The overall cluster mean rating of 3.06 indicates highly required. The low

standard deviation of 0.67 shows that the respondent's opinions do not differ remarkably to the itemized.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Educators with respect to organizational competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of mean scores of male and female Business Educators with respect to organizational competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	137	.222	394	.824	.12936	.58150	

Female

259

The result of t-test analysis in Table 4 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significance and 369 degree of freedom for the items is 0.222 with a significant value of 0.824. As the significant value of 0.824 is more than the 0.05 level of significance the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean scores of male and female Business Educators with respect to organizational competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State.

Discussion of Findings

The study in respect to research question one found the planning skills required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation for Business Educator Retirees in Imo State to includes; formulation of specific objectives for the private school, conduct a feasibility study for the school, advertisement of the school for admission and growth, obtain relevant information from experienced educationists, identify source of finance for starting the school, among others. The findings of the study were in consonance with Angiating (2016) who pointed that planning involves deciding on what the objectives of an organization will be, both quantitatively and qualitatively, while keeping in view the resources available to the organization. Simply put, planning involves setting up goals and objectives to be achieved. Ekwueme, Mbah and Onoh (2018) noted that basic management function involving the formulation of one or more detailed objective to achieve optimum balance of needs or demands with available resources based on adequate planning. This implies that the identified are the planning skills required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation for Business Educators' Retirees in Imo State. The findings also indicated that gender of the

teachers has no significant impact on the identified planning skills required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State. This was supported by Ekwueme, Mbah and Onoh (2018) that gender had no effect on the planning skills for effective managerial functions. Therefore, the identified skills are highly required by Teachers' Retirees effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State.

The finding according to research question two identified highly required organizational skills for effective management of Private Secondary Schools as; ability to recruit qualified teachers, select an experienced principal and other management staff, apply effective supervision of activities of the school, appoint a seasoned guidance councilor, form functional School Board Management Committee (SBMC), organize suitable train the trainers' workshop for teachers, apply management by objectives (MBO) for effective and efficient performance of staff, among others. These findings are supported by Eze and Ogbuegbu (2017) who noted that organizational skills enable one to supervise activities of the school. These organizational competencies as opined by Eze (2016) are an effective tool for teaching and management of the school day-to-day activities. This indicated that the identified are the organizational skills required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools. Furthermore, the findings of the hypothesis indicated that there was no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female Business Educators with respect to organizational skills required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation in Imo State. The implication of no significant different was that the gender had no influence on the identified organizational skills

required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation.

Conclusion

The study determined the competencies required teachers' retirees for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation. The study identified the planning competencies and organization competencies required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation. The identified competencies depicted the knowledge and skills required for effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation. These competencies have implication to the establishment and effective management of private schools for job creation to teachers' retirees as the identified competencies would provide the needed solution for competency-based education to teachers' retirees. The study therefore concludes that the identified competencies may be used to improve the effective management of Private Secondary Schools for sustainable job creation by teachers' retirees and others interested individuals. Based on the findings, the teachers at all levels and the government are expected to adopt the identified competencies in the retirement training of teachers interested in private school work. This is pertinent as there is need to achieve the desired growth, development in education and job creation through private school business based on the identified competencies.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Teacher's retirees going into private school business should acquire the identified competencies for effective management.
2. The government and concerned bodies for teachers' retirement should empower the teachers through retirement training on the competencies for managing private school businesses.

3. The teachers' retirees should develop adequate planning skills for proper and effective establishment and effective management.

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